

Lipids extraction from sewage sludge through *Green-biobased* solvents

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Abstract

In Europe, wastewater treatment produces around 10 million tonnes per year of sludge. Such a value is going to increase up to 13 million tonnes when Wastewater Directive (91/271/EEC) will be applied by 2020. On the other side, this waste could be considered as an interesting source to recovery components that can be used to obtain high added value products. In particular, the primary sewage sludge contains a significant amount of lipids that can be converted into biofuels. The lipids recovery from this biomass implies different challenges and is fundamental to determine the feasibility and costs of biofuel production using this feedstock.

This study reports the analysis of lipids extraction from sewage sludge using ethyl esters of volatile fatty acids (EEVFA). EEVFA are naturally occurring compounds, representing ones of the main constituents of flavour of fruits. They can be considered bioderivable solvents, since industrially obtainable through direct esterification of Ethanol and VFAs, which can be both produced through fermentation of exhausted feedstocks. In addition, they are easily hydrolysable in an aqueous environment, by regenerating ordinary species which are completely biodegradable. For all these reasons, the use of EEVFA as extracting solvents would minimize the environmental impact respect with conventional solvents (hexane is typically used).

A theoretical thermodynamic study of the lipids extraction was performed with an experimental matrix that emulated the chemical characteristics of a sewage sludge. This theoretical study was performed to obtain the phase diagrams for the lipids extraction and to identify the optimum operating conditions. A comparison of the lipids extraction using these green solvents and hexane was also performed. Then, the optimum conditions were tested and validated on real samples of sewage sludge, sampled from different municipal wastewater treatment plants.

Theoretical thermodynamic studies, as well as experimental evidences confirmed that ethyl butyrate was an alternative and effective green solvent to extract lipids from sludge.

Keywords: calcium soaps, sewage sludge, green extraction

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